

ANALYTICAL/EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF
CRACKING IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES UNDER BIAXIAL LOADING

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ABSTRACT

An interlaminar-shear-stress analysis was developed for deformation and progressive damage in biaxially loaded bi-directional three-layer composite laminates. The special cases of a crossply laminate under biaxial normal loading and shear loading discussed previously were combined [1-3]. The model gives closed form solutions for stress distributions, crack densities and reduced stiffnesses of the damaged layers and the laminate. The model was partially verified by conducting off-axis uniaxial tensile tests of $[0/90_2]_s$ crossply laminates. The stress-strain behavior, matrix cracking and the variation of engineering constants with matrix cracking was predicted and verified experimentally.

KEYWORDS: Crossply laminates; Biaxial Loading; Matrix Cracking; Stiffness Reduction; Constitutive relations; Damage state.

1. INTRODUCTION

A general interlaminar-shear-stress analysis was developed earlier by the authors for a $[\phi_m/\theta_n]_s$ bi-directional composite [1]. From this analysis a system of governing equations was derived for crossply laminates. This system can be solved to analyze crossply laminates with one or both layers cracked under different loading conditions by imposing appropriate boundary conditions. The cases of biaxial normal loading and pure shear loading were discussed previously [1,2,3]. Young's modulus and in-plane shear modulus reductions as a function of matrix cracking were predicted and verified experimentally. Here, the case of general biaxial loading is treated by combining the two cases before. Experimental corroboration was obtained by conducting uniaxial tensile tests on $[0/90_2]_s$ laminates at 10° from the 0° direction and monitoring deformations, cracking and mechanical properties with load.

2. ANALYTICAL MODEL

2.1 Governing Equations For crossply laminates the interlaminar-shear-stress analysis [1] provides the relationships among the through-the-thickness average displacements of each layer in the form of the following partial differential equations.

$$Q_{22}\bar{u}_{2,xx} + Q_{12}\bar{v}_{2,xy} + Q_{66}(\bar{u}_{2,yy} + \bar{v}_{2,xy}) = \frac{H_{11}}{h_2}(\bar{u}_2 - \bar{u}_1) \quad (1)$$

$$Q_{11}\bar{u}_{1,xx} + Q_{12}\bar{v}_{1,xy} + Q_{66}(\bar{u}_{1,yy} + \bar{v}_{1,xy}) = \frac{H_{11}}{h_1}(\bar{u}_1 - \bar{u}_2) \quad (2)$$

$$Q_{11}\bar{v}_{2,yy} + Q_{12}\bar{u}_{2,xy} + Q_{66}(\bar{v}_{2,xx} + \bar{u}_{2,xy}) = \frac{H_{22}}{h_2}(\bar{v}_2 - \bar{v}_1) \quad (3)$$

$$Q_{22}\bar{v}_{1,yy} + Q_{12}\bar{u}_{1,xy} + Q_{66}(\bar{v}_{1,xx} + \bar{u}_{1,xy}) = \frac{H_{22}}{h_1}(\bar{v}_1 - \bar{v}_2) \quad (4)$$

where Q_{11} , Q_{12} , Q_{22} and Q_{66} are stiffness parameters of the basic lamina; \bar{u}_1 , \bar{v}_1 , \bar{u}_2 and \bar{v}_2 are displacements of the 0° and 90° layers in the x - and y -directions; h_1 is thickness of the 0° layer; h_2 is the half thickness of the 90° layer (Fig. 1). H_{11} and H_{22} are interlaminar-shear-stress parameters given by

$$H_{11} = \frac{3 G_{13}G_{23}}{h_2G_{13} + h_1G_{23}}, \quad H_{22} = \frac{3 G_{13}G_{23}}{h_1G_{13} + h_2G_{23}}$$

G_{13} and G_{23} are out-of-plane shear moduli of the basic lamina.

$Q_{66} = G_{12}$ in-plane shear modulus.

2.2 Stress Distributions The most likely failure mode of a biaxially loaded crossply laminate is progressive cracking in one of the layers leading to ultimate failure. It has been shown analytically that as soon as the second layer begins to crack, the buildup of interlaminar stresses is so high that catastrophic failure follows quickly [3].

When one of the layers is cracked, say the 90° layer, the disturbance of the originally linear displacement field will be in the form of harmonic functions of x as follows:

$$\bar{u}_1 = C_1 x + C_2 y + C_5 \sinh(\alpha_1 x) \quad (5)$$

$$\bar{u}_2 = C_1 x + C_2 y + C_6 \sinh(\alpha_1 x) \quad (6)$$

$$\bar{v}_1 = C_3 x + C_4 y + C_7 \sinh(\alpha_2 x) \quad (7)$$

$$\bar{v}_2 = C_3 x + C_4 y + C_8 \sinh(\alpha_2 x) \quad (8)$$

Substituting the above in the governing equations (1-4) we obtain

$$\alpha_1^2 = H_{11} \left(\frac{1}{h_1 Q_{11}} + \frac{1}{h_2 Q_{11}} \right) \quad (9)$$

$$\alpha_2^2 = \frac{H_{22}}{Q_{66}} \left(\frac{1}{h_1} + \frac{1}{h_2} \right) \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{C_6}{C_5} = -\frac{h_1}{h_2} \frac{Q_{11}}{Q_{22}} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{C_7}{C_8} = -\frac{h_2}{h_1} \quad (11)$$

Using appropriate boundary conditions, e.g., stress-free crack boundary and prescribed displacements in terms of average laminate strains we obtain the following relations for the layer stresses as a function of average laminate strains, crack spacing and residual stresses:

$$\sigma_{1x} = Q_{11} \left[\bar{\epsilon}_x + C_5 \left[\frac{\alpha_1 \cosh(\alpha_1 x)}{\sinh(\alpha_1 \ell_x / 2)} - \frac{2}{\ell_x} \right] \right] + Q_{12} \bar{\epsilon}_y - \sigma_{2x}^R \frac{h_2}{h_1} \quad (12)$$

$$\sigma_{1y} = Q_{12} \left[\bar{\epsilon}_x + C_5 \left[\frac{\alpha_1 \cosh(\alpha_1 x)}{\sinh(\alpha_1 \ell_x / 2)} - \frac{2}{\ell_x} \right] \right] + Q_{22} \bar{\epsilon}_y + \sigma_{1y}^R \quad (13)$$

$$\tau_{1xy} = \bar{\tau}_{xy} \left[1 + \frac{h_2}{h_1} \frac{\cosh(\alpha_2 x)}{\cosh(\alpha_2 \ell_x / 2)} \right] \quad (14)$$

$$\sigma_{2x} = Q_{22} \left[\bar{\epsilon}_x - C_5 \left[\frac{Q_{11} h_1}{Q_{22} h_2} \frac{\alpha_1 \cosh(\alpha_1 x)}{\sinh(\alpha_1 \ell_x / 2)} + \frac{2}{\ell_x} \right] \right] + Q_{12} \bar{\epsilon}_y + \sigma_{2x}^R \quad (15)$$

$$\sigma_{2y} = Q_{12} \left[\bar{\epsilon}_x - C_5 \left[\frac{Q_{11} h_1}{Q_{22} h_2} \frac{\alpha_1 \cosh(\alpha_1 x)}{\sinh(\alpha_1 \ell_x / 2)} + \frac{2}{\ell_x} \right] \right] + Q_{11} \bar{\epsilon}_y - \sigma_{1y}^R \frac{h_1}{h_2} \quad (16)$$

$$\tau_{2xy} = \bar{\tau}_{xy} \left[1 - \frac{\cosh(\alpha_2 x)}{\cosh(\alpha_2 \ell_x / 2)} \right] \quad (17)$$

where ℓ_x = crack spacing

$\bar{\epsilon}_x, \bar{\epsilon}_y$ = average laminate strains

$\sigma_{1x}^R, \sigma_{1y}^R, \sigma_{2x}^R, \sigma_{2y}^R$ = residual stresses in layers 1 and 2 in the x- and y- directions.

The remaining constant C_5 is obtained from equilibrium conditions as

$$C_5 = (\bar{\epsilon}_x + \frac{Q_{12}}{Q_{22}} \bar{\epsilon}_y + \frac{1}{Q_{22}} \sigma_{2x}^R) / W_x \quad (18)$$

$$W_x = \frac{Q_{11} h_1}{Q_{22} h_2} \alpha_1 \coth\left(\frac{\alpha_1 \ell_x}{2}\right) + \frac{2}{\ell_x} \quad (19)$$

2.3 Stress-Strain Relations The above lead to the following relations between laminate strains, applied laminate stresses, crack spacing and residual stresses:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \bar{\epsilon}_x \\ \bar{\epsilon}_y \\ \bar{\gamma}_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{I_{22}(h_1 + h_2)}{I_{11}I_{22} - I_{12}^2} & \frac{-I_{12}(h_1 + h_2)}{I_{11}I_{22} - I_{12}^2} & 0 \\ \frac{-I_{12}(h_1 + h_2)}{I_{11}I_{22} - I_{12}^2} & \frac{I_{11}(h_1 + h_2)}{I_{11}I_{22} - I_{12}^2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{\rho_G Q_{66}} \end{bmatrix} \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\sigma}_x \\ \bar{\sigma}_y \\ \bar{\tau}_{xy} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} J_{11} \\ J_{21} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \sigma_{2x}^R \right\} \quad (20)$$

where

$$I_{11} = Q_{11}h_1 + Q_{22}h_2 - (Q_{11}h_1 + Q_{22}h_2) \frac{2}{\ell_x W_x} \quad (21)$$

$$I_{12} = Q_{12}h_1 + Q_{12}h_2 - (Q_{11}h_1 + Q_{22}h_2) \frac{Q_{12}}{Q_{22}} \frac{2}{\ell_x W_x} \quad (22)$$

$$I_{22} = Q_{22}h_1 + Q_{11}h_2 - (Q_{11}h_1 + Q_{22}h_2) \frac{Q_{12}^2}{Q_{22}^2} \frac{2}{\ell_x W_x} \quad (23)$$

$$J_{11} = \frac{(Q_{11}h_1 + Q_{22}h_2)}{(h_1+h_2)} \frac{2}{\ell_x W_x} \frac{1}{Q_{22}} \quad (24)$$

$$J_{21} = \frac{(Q_{11}h_1 + Q_{22}h_2)}{(h_1+h_2)} \frac{Q_{12}}{Q_{22}} \frac{2}{\ell_x W_x} \frac{1}{Q_{22}} \quad (25)$$

The shear modulus reduction ratio ρ_G is [2]:

$$\rho_G = \left[1 + \frac{h_2}{h_1} \frac{2}{\alpha_2 \ell_x} \tanh\left(\frac{\alpha_2 \ell_x}{2}\right) \right]^{-1} \quad (26)$$

Equation (20) can be substituted into eqs. (12-17) to obtain expressions for the layer stresses as a function of applied laminate stresses, crack density and residual stresses. The layer stresses, e.g., σ_{2x} , σ_{2y} and τ_{2xy} can be substituted into a selected failure criterion, such as the Tsai-Wu criterion, to obtain the crack spacing for the given applied loading. Thus, a loading versus crack spacing curve can be obtained.

2.4 Laminate Elastic Parameters The laminate compliance matrix referred to the x-y coordinate system is given in eq. (20) as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} S_{xx} & S_{xy} & 0 \\ S_{xy} & S_{yy} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & S_{ss} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{I_{22}(h_1 + h_2)}{I_{11}I_{22} - I_{12}^2} & \frac{-I_{12}(h_1 + h_2)}{I_{11}I_{22} - I_{12}^2} & 0 \\ \frac{-I_{12}(h_1 + h_2)}{I_{11}I_{22} - I_{12}^2} & \frac{I_{11}(h_1 + h_2)}{I_{11}I_{22} - I_{12}^2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{\rho_G Q_{66}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (27)$$

The transformed laminate compliances referred to the \tilde{x} - \tilde{y} coordinate system (Fig. 2) are

$$\left. \begin{aligned} S_{\tilde{x}\tilde{x}} &= S_{xx} m^4 + (2 S_{xy} + S_{ss}) n^2 m^2 + S_{yy} n^4 \\ S_{\tilde{x}\tilde{y}} &= S_{xy} (n^4 + m^4) + (S_{xx} + S_{yy} - S_{ss}) n^2 m^2 \\ S_{\tilde{y}\tilde{y}} &= S_{xx} n^4 + (2 S_{xy} + S_{ss}) n^2 m^2 + S_{yy} m^4 \\ S_{\tilde{x}\tilde{s}} &= (2 S_{xx} - 2 S_{xy} - S_{yy}) n m^3 - (2 S_{yy} - 2 S_{xy} - S_{ss}) n^3 m \\ S_{\tilde{y}\tilde{s}} &= (2 S_{xx} - 2 S_{xy} - S_{ss}) n^3 m - (2 S_{yy} - 2 S_{xy} - S_{ss}) n m^3 \\ S_{\tilde{s}\tilde{s}} &= 2 (2 S_{xx} + 2 S_{yy} - 4 S_{xy} - S_{ss}) n^2 m^2 + S_{ss} (n^4 + m^4) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (28)$$

$$m = \cos(\theta), n = \sin(\theta)$$

They are related to the engineering constants by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \overline{S_{xx}} & \overline{S_{xy}} & \overline{S_{xs}} \\ \overline{S_{xy}} & \overline{S_{yy}} & \overline{S_{ys}} \\ \overline{S_{xs}} & \overline{S_{ys}} & \overline{S_{ss}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\overline{E_x}} & -\frac{\overline{v_{yx}}}{\overline{E_y}} & \frac{\overline{\eta_{sx}}}{\overline{G_{xy}}} \\ -\frac{\overline{v_{xy}}}{\overline{E_x}} & \frac{1}{\overline{E_y}} & \frac{\overline{\eta_{sy}}}{\overline{G_{xy}}} \\ \frac{\overline{\eta_{xs}}}{\overline{E_x}} & \frac{\overline{\eta_{ys}}}{\overline{E_y}} & \frac{1}{\overline{G_{xy}}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (29)$$

Thus, the off-axis engineering constants, Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio and shear coupling coefficient are:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \overline{E_x} &= 1 / \overline{S_{xx}} \\ \overline{v_{xy}} &= -\overline{S_{xy}} / \overline{S_{xx}} \\ \overline{\eta_{xs}} &= \overline{S_{xs}} / \overline{S_{xx}} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (30)$$

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The analytical model described before was tested by conducting experiments on crossply laminates subjected to biaxial loading. Graphite/epoxy (AS4/3501-6) $[0/90_2]_s$ crossply laminates were tested under uniaxial tensile loading $\overline{\sigma_x}$ at an angle θ to the 0° -layer direction (Fig. 2). The state of stress after transformation to the x-y coordinate system (laminate coordinate system) is expressed as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \overline{\sigma_x} \\ \overline{\sigma_y} \\ \overline{\tau_{xy}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} m^2 \\ n^2 \\ -m n \end{bmatrix} \overline{\sigma_x} \quad (31)$$

Thus, an element of the laminate shown in Fig. 1 is subjected to a general in-plane biaxial state of stress referred to its principal directions.

Test coupons were machined at an angle of 10° with the 0° -ply direction, tabbed with glass/epoxy tabs and instrumented with 3-gage rosettes. Three strain components were monitored during the test, $\overline{\epsilon_x}$, $\overline{\epsilon_y}$ and $\overline{\epsilon}_{45}$ (at 45° with the loading axis), from which the shear strain $\overline{\gamma_{xy}}$ was computed. The specimens were loaded in steps to failure. At each load level the strain readings were recorded and an X-radiograph obtained, in which cracking was observed and measured.

The applied stress $\overline{\sigma_x}$ was plotted versus the three measured (and computed) strain components $\overline{\epsilon_x}$, $\overline{\epsilon_y}$ and $\overline{\gamma_{xy}}$ in Fig. 3 and compared with analytical predictions from eqs. (20). A sharp discontinuity in these curves corresponds to the onset of matrix cracking in the 90° layer. The agreement between measured and predicted behavior is satisfactory.

X-radiographs obtained at various applied stress levels are shown in Fig. 4 where the stress level and the measured crack density are marked. The applied stress was then plotted versus the measured crack density in Fig. 5. Results are in good agreement with

predictions obtained from eqs. (15) and (20) using a maximum stress failure criterion.

Three engineering constants were obtained from the experimental data, Young's modulus $\bar{E}_{\bar{x}}$, Poisson's ratio $\bar{\nu}_{\bar{x}\bar{y}}$ and shear coupling coefficient $\bar{\eta}_{\bar{x}\bar{s}}$. They were obtained at different load levels and damage states (crack densities) as follows:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \bar{E}_{\bar{x}} &= d\bar{\sigma}_{\bar{x}} / d\bar{\epsilon}_{\bar{x}} \\ \bar{\nu}_{\bar{x}\bar{y}} &= -d\bar{\epsilon}_{\bar{y}} / d\bar{\epsilon}_{\bar{x}} \\ \bar{\eta}_{\bar{x}\bar{s}} &= d\bar{\gamma}_{\bar{x}\bar{y}} / d\bar{\epsilon}_{\bar{x}} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (31)$$

The above constants were plotted versus measured crack spacing in Fig. 6 in normalized form, by dividing each property value by its original value for the undamaged laminate. The predictions from the theoretical model obtained by eqs. (27), (28), and (30) are in good agreement with the experimental results.

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

An analytical model based on an interlaminar-shear-stress analysis of bidirectional composites was applied to the case of a crossply laminate under general in-plane biaxial loading. Closed form expressions were obtained for layer stresses and stress-strain relations for the laminate as a function of loading, damage state (matrix cracking) and residual stresses. The model was verified by off-axis testing of $[0/90_2]_s$ crossply laminates. Measured stress-strain behavior, damage evolution, and elastic constant degradation were in good agreement with the corresponding predictions by the proposed model.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work described here was sponsored by the Office of Naval Research (ONR). We are grateful to Dr. Yapa Rajapakse of ONR for his encouragement and cooperation and to Mrs. Yolande Mallian for typing the manuscript.

6. REFERENCES

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FIGURE 1. Crossply laminate with transverse cracks

FIGURE 2. Loading and laminate coordinate systems

FIGURE 3. Stress-strain curves for [0/90₂]_s graphite/epoxy laminate under 10° off-axis tensile loading

	(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)
Stress, $\bar{\sigma}_x$ MPa(ksi)	162 (23.4)	212 (30.7)	254 (36.9)	312 (45.2)
Crack Density, λ_x 1/cm (1/in)	0.0 (0.0)	1.6 (4.2)	5.9 (15.0)	9.1 (23.0)

FIGURE 4. X-radiographs of $[0/90_2]_s$ graphite/epoxy specimens at various levels of 10° off-axis tensile loading

FIGURE 5. Applied stress vs. crack density of $[0/90_2]_s$ graphite/epoxy laminate under 10° off-axis tensile loading

FIGURE 6. Engineering constants as a function of crack density for $[0/90_2]_s$ graphite/epoxy laminate at 10° off-axis direction